

1 **NLRP13 functions in the early embryo between the 1-cell and 8-cell stages.**

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7 We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation
8 resulting in the first 3 cell divisions from 1-cell, 2-cell, and 4-cell stages. We describe here activation of the
9 NLR family receptor NLRP13 in the human embryo in early human development. NLRP13 functions are
10 not widely understood.

11 Citations

12 Caldiran, F.Y., Deveci, K. and Cacan, E., 2023. NLRP13 inflammasome complex is hypermethylated in
13 familial Mediterranean fever and global methylation correlates with the disease severity. *Annals of human
14 genetics*, 87(3), pp.115-124.